

INNER CONFLICT AND MOTIVATIONAL DISINTEGRATION IN ADOLESCENTS. CROSS-CULTURAL INVESTIGATION

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Abstract

Throughout life, everyone has experienced various inner conflicts related to certain situations or areas of life. However, today, more than ever, adolescents are facing inner conflicts which affect them quite deeply and determine them to experience a tension that sometimes translates into an existential crisis. This is due to the mental dispute between what they really want and what a society can offer them through the availability of life spheres. Thus, this research work focuses on the interdependence between the value and availability of various areas of life, which influence the motivation of adolescents, being an accurate indicator of their inner conflicts.

Keywords: adolescent, immigrant, inner conflict, availability, value, area of life, feeling of inner emptiness.

Introduction

The feeling of inner conflict is a diffuse and poorly outlined feeling, especially due to its ambiguous characteristics which cause a lot of anxiety in adolescents. The psychological distress associated with this feeling is big, because the adolescent who is suffering from it cannot find a clear symptom with which to associate it. For this reason, this feeling is hard to define and hard to bear, because it is not easy to describe, to put into words and to delimit in the context of internal and external reality what a person experiences on an emotional level, because the boundaries in this sense are blurred.

Sometimes it can be really difficult to choose between certainties, desires and duties. Confusion is a sign that we are experiencing internal deadlock or conflict between opposing aspects, as we cannot find a solution between different needs and demands at that moment.

The term *inner conflict* refers to the experience where there are conflicting beliefs, desires, impulses, or psychological feelings. Psychology also uses the term *cognitive dissonance*, which translates into conflicting and inconsistent attitudes. A mental battle can occur at any point in a person's life, regardless of their field: relational, value, religious, moral, erotic, socio-ideological, etc.

Adolescents' inner conflict will be discussed in this study in relation to the axiological sphere and specific areas of life. Thus, we will analyze the internal psychological tension, translated into existential conflict, that discomfort and confusion about life and its future, fuelled by the perception of adolescents' powerlessness to have what they really want.

Methodology and methods

This investigative research has the aim to obtain an overview of the inner conflict, connected to certain spheres of life and which is perceived by both Moldovan adolescents in the Republic of Moldova and Moldovan adolescents in Italy. Thus, this objective provides us with an additional piece of issues related to some particularities of age and migration circumstances, being a sketch of the young generation in the

diaspora in terms of the characteristics imposed by immigration status and the mechanisms by which this status influences adolescents' values.

Research aim: To investigate the inner conflict related to the axiological sphere in Moldovan adolescents from different ethnocultural backgrounds.

The subject of the investigation was to identify the impact of the sociocultural environment on the experience of inner conflict in adolescents.

Consequently, our goals were the following:

1. To investigate the inner conflict in adolescents;
2. To determine the level of disintegration in the sphere of personal motivation in adolescents.

For this purpose, the questionnaire on *The Value-Accessibility Ratio in Various Life Areas*, developed by E. B. Fantalova (Достанова, Кнорре, Климова, 1997), was administered. It has also been used quite widely by other researchers (Baciu, 2014, pp. 57-76; Secheiko, 2018, pp. 9-14; Tarnovschi, 2017, pp. 102-105; 8).

The questionnaire on *The Value-Accessibility Ratio in Various Life Areas* contains 12 values: *An active lifestyle; Health; Interesting jobs; Beauty of nature and art; Love; Material wealth; Presence of good friends; Self-confidence; Knowledge; Independence and freedom of action; Happy family life; Creation.*

The values are represented in 2 matrices. Each of these values matches a numerical rating. Thus, the respondents are instructed to select only one numerical rating from each cell. This way, no pair is omitted. Matrix 1 represents the choice of the most important value, while Matrix 2 represents the choice of the most accessible value in the near future. As a result, the choices of the subjects are counted and this allows us to obtain a total score for each value (Фанталова, 2011).

The research took place between December, 2018 and October, 2019. Accordingly, the research sample consisted of 215 adolescents (110, being from Moldova, Chișinău and Florești and 105, being from Italy, Lombardia, Emilia-Romagna, Liguria and Veneto). The adolescents were between 14 and 18 years old.

Results and discussions

The following results emerged from the investigation:

Based on the average indicators of different areas of life, the spheres generating *anxiety and psychological concern* were delimited. Figure 1 shows the data on the number of young people experiencing inner conflict in each area of life.

Assessment of inner conflicts among Moldovan adolescents in the Republic of Moldova

Figure 1. Assessment of inner conflicts among Moldovan adolescents in the Republic of Moldova

Figure 1 clearly indicates that there is a high number of adolescents with inner conflicts.

The conflicts that are the most prominent are associated with spheres such as *Independence and freedom of action* (87,3%), *A happy family life* (69,1%), and *Health* (59,1%). It is apparent that Moldovan adolescents in the Republic of Moldova view the prospect of possessing them as problematic.

In terms of *Independence and freedom of action*, we can notice that today's adolescents are likely to feel a lot of pressure from the entourage "to be in line with something", which certainly bothers them, as they have the characteristic need of their age to define themselves, to be independent and implicitly demanding the possibility to be responsible.

At the same time, they want a *Happy family life*, not with "friendly" parents, but with rules and limits that give them security, in which they feel appreciated

and accepted. They also see the meaning of the "happy family" in the relationships between its members, who help each other, support each other and love each other unconditionally. However, adolescents find it inconceivable and "hard to draw", which is putting pressure on them.

Regarding *Health*, adolescents described distrust of their ability to be in good health in the future. This fact indicates that adolescents are highly concerned about their health, but they are unsure if they can maintain it. Thus, we can assume that today's generation looks with skepticism at the quality of air, food, all of which creates psychological problems for them. Similarly, this concern may also be caused by the shortcomings of the medical system in the Republic of Moldova, fuelling adolescents' distrust in the skills of medical staff.

Assessment of inner conflicts among Moldovan immigrant adolescents in Italy

Figure 2. Assessment of inner conflicts among Moldovan immigrant adolescents in Italy

Figure 2 highlights the fact that immigrant adolescents have fairly pronounced inner conflicts. The most obvious conflicts refer to *Interesting jobs* (83,8%), *Material wealth* (78,1%), *Independence and freedom of action* (59%), *Happy family life* (59%), *Knowledge* (52,4%) and *Presence of good friends* (49,5%).

In relation to *Interesting jobs*, adolescents are aware that immigrants do not have free access to the labor market, so they are distrustful of attractive jobs.

A similar explanation is given for *Material wealth*, where the categories of jobs reserved for immigrants are less well paid and cannot guarantee financial stability, compared to the native population, as they are seasonal or strictly fixed-term and this is perceived by adolescents as a form of discrimination, causing them inner conflicts, which they find more difficult to cope with (Roșca, Caunenco, 2019, pp. 214-220). In addition, this sphere, being linked to work, can also be seen as a kind of recognition of personal involvement and capabilities or as a necessary means to live independently.

The value of *Independence and freedom of action* seems to be limited in the future of young people, too. This can interfere with the "condition of the foreigner", which is felt harshly by adolescents in the diaspora, as well as the freedom and right to choose Italian citizenship, which is a painful key for some of them. Thus, even if Italy is a democratic country, with solid principles related to freedom, in the case of foreigners it is quite reserved in terms of their access to different areas of public life "freedom, for young immigrants, is a

multi-semantic term, which is linked to democracy, the possibility of participating in collective decisions and equal opportunities, the freedom to fulfill yourself in the society where you grew up and to do what you want to do" (Shchwartz, 1992, pp. 1-65).

Inner conflicts, related to the *Happy family life*, arise among immigrant adolescents, too. This value is seen in gloomy colors as a future perspective for adolescents, because they have already had the experience of family reunification, which left a painful mark on some of them and eroded the image of the *Happy family* in Italy.

In this context, *Knowledge* is also considered to be a sphere that is far from being available to young Moldovans. This is related to both the limited access to some educational institutions due to bureaucratic tactics, insufficient financial resources to cover tuition fees, and the disadvantaged position of the immigrant, all of which block the possibility of *Knowledge* at the middle or high school level (Roșca, 2021, pp. 172-181).

No less problematic, the sphere related to *The presence of good friends* is also seen. Immigrant adolescents have the difficulty of trusting the network of friends in the future. Even if this meets their need for protection, autonomy and recognition, over time, it can cause various forms of ethnic segregation, preventing their social integration in this way.

Furthermore, we intended to assess the feeling of inner emptiness in Moldovan adolescents in the Republic of Moldova and Moldovan immigrant adolescents in Italy.

Figure 3. Assessing the feeling of inner emptiness in Moldovan adolescents in the Republic of Moldova

As shown in Figure 3, the feeling of inner emptiness is related only to Beauty of nature and art.

Figure 4. Assessing the feeling of inner emptiness in Moldovan immigrant adolescents in Italy

Figure 4 shows that immigrant adolescents have more inner conflicts than feelings of inner emptiness. The most pronounced feeling of inner emptiness is related to *The beauty of nature and art*.

Of particular interest is the degree of interdependence between *value* and *availability* of spheres of life for adolescents. This concept is based on the fact that the determining factors of the personal motivational sphere are fluctuating and gradually change depending on the circumstances of life, between the two planes of consciousness: the plan containing awareness of values, personal intentions, objectives for the future and

the plan related to accessibility, implementation of specific objectives, easily achievable, located in "visible psychological field" (Secheiko, 2018, pp. 9-14). In this sense, "value" and "availability" are not polar characteristics of the personal motivational sphere, but on the contrary, the stimulating power of different motives and the presence of inner conflicts, related to certain spheres of life, which largely depend on the nature of the relationship between "value" and "availability", reflecting the degree of mismatch and disintegration in the motivational sphere. As a result, this indicates the level of dissatisfaction with the current life situation, the presence of inner conflicts, the blockage of basic

needs, on the one hand, and the level of self-realization, self-harmony, integration and internal identity, on the other.

Therefore for optimal assessment, it is important to recognize the nature and degree of dissociation (discrepancy) between "valuable" and "available", con-

nected to the main spheres of life, namely the divergence between what "is now" and what "should be", between "I want" and "I have", as well as between "I will" and "I can".

A picture of the levels of disintegration in the personal motivational sphere is shown in Figure 5.

Figure 5. Levels of disintegration in the sphere of personal motivation in Moldovan adolescents in the Republic of Moldova and Moldovan immigrant adolescents in Italy

Figure 5 shows that 84,5% of adolescents in the Republic of Moldova have a low level of disintegration in the sphere of personal motivation and 15,5% - medium level, while 43,8% of immigrant adolescents in Italy have a low level, 55,2% - medium level and 1,0% - high level.

Thus, in order to portray the complexity of the feeling of disintegration in the motivational sphere, present in the profile of the contemporary adolescent, we have resorted again to comparisons of the level of disintegration in the sphere of personal motivation (R) in Moldovan adolescents in the Republic of Moldova and Moldovan adolescents in Italy, which we obtained using the Mann-Whitney U Test.

Therefore, based on the obtained result ($U=3414$, $Z=-6.246$, $p<0,001$) following the comparisons of disintegration levels in the sphere of personal motivation, we observed the existence of significant differences between the two groups of adolescents, where Moldovan adolescents in Italy have a significantly higher level of disintegration than adolescents in the Republic of Moldova.

In order to have a clearer picture, we tried to compare the levels of disintegration in the sphere of personal motivation according to gender and place of living. Thus, after comparing the level of disintegration in the sphere of personal motivation (R), obtained by adolescent girls and adolescent boys in Italy U

($U=1156,5$, $Z=-1,330$, $p=0,183 >0,05$), we noticed the lack of statistically significant differences in this regard. However, statistically significant differences were observed between adolescent girls and adolescent boys in the Republic of Moldova ($U=1036$, $Z=-3,958$, $p<0,001$), where adolescent boys have demonstrated a significantly higher level of disintegration, compared to adolescent girls.

At the same time, we compared the results obtained by Moldovan adolescent girls in the Republic of Moldova and Moldovan adolescent girls in Italy. In this sense, statistically significant differences ($U=801,5$, $Z=-5,472$, $p<0,001$) are highlighted. Thus, Moldovan adolescent girls in Italy had a significantly higher level of disintegration than adolescent girls in the Republic of Moldova. The same thing was noted in the results of comparisons between Moldovan adolescent boys in the Republic of Moldova and Moldovan adolescent boys in Italy ($U=943$, $Z=-2,921$, $p<0,01$). In this regard, having confirmed the existence of statistically significant differences, we can state that Moldovan adolescent boys in Italy show a significantly higher level of disintegration than Moldovan adolescent boys in the Republic of Moldova.

CONCLUSIONS

1. In terms of internal psychological tension, related to certain spheres of life, the number of adoles-

cents with inner conflicts, both in the Republic of Moldova and in Italy, is quite high. In this sense, it is remarkable that some spheres of life, for both groups of young people, generate anxiety and psychological concern, which suggests the distrust of young people in certain institutions and systems, which are influenced by both the Moldovan and Italian social context.

2. Based on the interdependence between the value and availability of spheres of life, the levels of disintegration in the motivational sphere of adolescents were outlined, which reflects their state of dissatisfaction with the current situation regarding the spheres of life, the presence of conflicts and internal blockages related to self-realization, integration and identity. Thus, the majority of adolescents in Moldova have a low level of disintegration in the sphere of personal motivation, while adolescents in Italy, more than half, have a medium level. This translates into the fact that the characteristics of the sociocultural context in which the socialization of adolescents takes place have a significant impact on both their value sphere and inner motivation.

3. The comparative results of the levels of disintegration in the sphere of personal motivation according to gender and place of living reveal the following conclusions:

a) Adolescent boys in the Republic of Moldova demonstrate a higher level of motivational disintegration compared to adolescent girls in the Republic of Moldova;

b) Moldovan adolescent girls in Italy show a statistically significant higher level of disintegration compared to adolescent girls in the Republic of Moldova;

c) Moldovan adolescent boys in Italy have a higher level of motivational disintegration than Moldovan adolescent boys.

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